

A numerical approach on the verification of parameter retrieval techniques for composite periodic electromagnetic media

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Abstract – A new technique is proposed for the confirmation of the accuracy of effective parameter retrieval techniques for composite periodic electromagnetic media. The retrieved effective parameters are inserted into the analytical relations of wave propagation in a complex homogeneous medium and a reconstructed dispersion diagram is formed. This diagram is then compared to the original dispersion diagram returned by the eigenvalue analysis of the composite inhomogeneous structure and the discrepancies between them are determined.

I. INTRODUCTION

A great variety of techniques has been published in recent years for the efficient retrieval of the effective parameters of electromagnetically complex periodic media. Among them, the most popular approach has been the S-parameter techniques, based on the Nicolson-Ross-Weir method [1, 2]: Utilizing the inversion of Fresnel coefficients' relations for a homogeneous slab, they return the effective permittivity and permeability of a composite periodic medium (subsequent extended versions of these techniques also include magnetoelectric coupling coefficients [3, 4]). Recently, a robust parameter retrieval technique was proposed, which utilizes the eigenvalue information of the dispersion diagrams and the averaging of the field components of the supported electromagnetic modes in order to return the tensors of permittivity $\bar{\epsilon}_r$, permeability $\bar{\mu}_r$ and magnetoelectric coupling $\bar{\kappa}$ [5].

In homogenization techniques, the assessment of the accuracy of the returned effective parameters has always been an issue. In many cases, there have been ambiguities in the results, which often have to do with the signs of their real and imaginary part values. In this work, we propose a new approach to assess the accuracy of any parameter retrieval technique existing in the literature: Taking the retrieved parameters of a homogenized medium, we utilize the analytical dispersion relations of the wave propagation in such a medium to produce a reconstructed version of its dispersion diagram. Then, we compare this with the original dispersion diagram of the composite structure and determine the discrepancies between them. The success of the retrieval technique is, therefore, measured in terms of the consistency between the intrinsic behavior of the composite medium (its original dispersion diagram) and the reconstructed version of it, which comes from the homogenized medium approach, as a result of the utilized parameter retrieval technique.

II. EIGENMODES AND RETRIEVED PARAMETERS OF A COMPLEX PERIODIC MEDIUM

We utilize the parameter retrieval technique proposed in [5] to obtain the effective electromagnetic parameters of a composite periodic medium consisting of edge-coupled split-ring resonators (EC-SRRs) repeated in an orthorhombic lattice. A unit cell of the simulated structure is illustrated in Fig. 1(a) and the geometric details of the resonator are given in Fig. 1(b). The proposed technique makes use of the numerical eigenvalue information and the averaging of the field quantities at the unit cell's facets. More specifically, the dispersion diagrams of a periodic medium at all three orthogonal propagation directions are formed (k_x , k_y and k_z , where $k = \beta - j\alpha$ is the complex propagation constant), and the supported modes at every frequency are returned [6, 7]. Subsequently, the tangentially continuous field components are averaged at the edges of the unit cell, whereas the normally continuous field components are averaged at the facets of the unit cell. An algebraic system consisting of the effective

Fig. 1: (a) Unit cell of the EC-SRR medium. The resonators are arranged on a cubic lattice (the edge of the cube is $d = d_x = d_y = d_z = 8.8$ mm) (b) Dimensions of the EC-SRR in mm: The metallic rings are made of copper and have a thickness of $17 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Original dispersion diagram of the EC-SRR medium for k_x propagation. Lightline modes are illustrated in black. Propagating SRR modes are plotted in blue, evanescent SRR modes with large propagation constant in green and evanescent SRR modes with small propagation constant in red.

Fig. 2: Real and imaginary parts of the effective material parameters for the EC-SRR medium.

electromagnetic parameters as unknowns is solved for every simulated frequency and their complex values are obtained.

The dispersion diagram for the case of k_x propagation is depicted in Fig. 1(c). There, the presence of two supported modes is observed: The lightline mode, where the electromagnetic field does not interact with the medium, and the SRR mode, where the interaction of the electromagnetic field with the medium results in the well-known magnetic resonant behavior [6]. In Fig. 2 the real and imaginary parts of the retrieved effective parameters of the simulated medium are depicted. It is observed that a resonant behavior is exhibited for $\mu_{r,zz,\text{eff}}$, $\epsilon_{r,yy,\text{eff}}$ and $\kappa_{yz,\text{eff}}$ at the bandgap frequency range (5.3 – 6 GHz approximately). This way, the expected behavior of magnetic dipole formation at microscopic level is confirmed, normal to the scatterers' plane, along with the existence of an electric dipole in y -direction and magnetoelectric coupling at yz -directions, owing to the lack of symmetry of the resonators with respect to the yz -plane [7, 8].

III. WAVE PROPAGATION IN A HOMOGENIZED MEDIUM

At this point, we present the technique for the verification of the retrieved electromagnetic parameters. To this end, we assume wave propagation in a *homogeneous medium*, with its electromagnetic properties equal to the values of the retrieved effective parameters in Section II. It is reminded that an EC-SRR periodic medium belongs to the category of omega bianisotropic media. In this type of media (assuming wave propagation at x -axis), only electromagnetic parameters $\mu_{r,zz,\text{eff}}$, $\epsilon_{r,yy,\text{eff}}$ and $\kappa_{yz,\text{eff}}$ are present (all other diagonal elements of $\bar{\epsilon}_r$ and $\bar{\mu}_r$ are equal to 1 and the rest of the magnetoelectric coupling coefficients in $\bar{\kappa}$ are equal to 0). Subsequently, we utilize the existing analytical dispersion relations for such a medium in the literature, which relate the complex propagation constant k with angular frequency ω [9, 10, 11, 12]. For the first mode supported by the medium, the complex propagation constant is given by $k_1 = (\omega/c_0)\sqrt{\epsilon_{r,yy}\mu_{r,zz} - k_{yz}^2}$ and it corresponds to the SRR mode (where c_0 is the speed of light in vacuum). The lightline mode, which is also supported, has a propagation constant $k_2 = (\omega/c_0)\sqrt{\epsilon_{r,zz}\mu_{r,yy}}$. We now compare the reconstructed dispersion diagram with the original one, see Fig. 3

Fig. 3: Original and reconstructed dispersion diagrams of the investigated EC-SRR medium for k_x incidence. Real and imaginary part of the complex propagation constant $\beta - j\alpha$.

for this comparison. We find a perfect agreement between the original and the reconstructed values of the complex propagation constants for both the lightline mode and the SRR mode. For the lightline mode, the percentage difference between the original and the reconstructed real parts does not exceed 1%, whereas for the SRR mode it increases to 4%. A very significant point that should be stressed is the fact that there is no sign change in the values of the reconstructed propagation constants, especially inside the bandgap frequencies. It is deduced that the results of the parameter retrieval technique, when utilized as the electromagnetic parameters of a homogeneous medium, accomplish to successfully reproduce the original dispersion diagram, which is the fingerprint of a composite periodic medium.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have successfully reproduced the dispersion diagram of a composite periodic medium by assuming wave propagation inside a homogeneous medium with electromagnetic parameters equal to the retrieved effective parameters of the initial, inhomogeneous medium. The results are in perfect agreement, illustrating the robustness of our technique. The proposed process may be utilised by any homogenization technique for the assessment of the accuracy of their returned results.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Smith, D., Vier, D., Koschny, T. and Soukoulis, C. "Electromagnetic parameter retrieval from inhomogeneous metamaterials," *Physical Review E*, **71**, 036617 (2005)
- [2] B. W. Weir "Automatic measurement of complex dielectric constant and permeability at microwave frequencies," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, **62**, 33-36 (1974)
- [3] Zhao, R., Koschny, T. and Soukoulis, C. "Chiral metamaterials: retrieval of the effective parameters with and without substrate," *Optics Express*, **18**, 14553-14567 (2010)
- [4] Hasar, U., Buldu, G., Kaya, Y. and Ozturk, G. "Determination of effective constitutive parameters of inhomogeneous metamaterials with bianisotropy," *IEEE Transactions On Microwave Theory And Techniques*, **66**, 3734-3744 (2018)
- [5] Nitas M. and Yioultis T. V., "Electromagnetic parameter retrieval technique utilizing eigenvalue analysis and field averaging," *Journal of Applied Physics*, **131**, 114902 (2022)
- [6] Nitas M. and Yioultis T. V., "Characterization of edge-coupled broadside-coupled and complementary split-ring resonator periodic media based on numerical solutions of eigenvalue problems," *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, **69**, 5259-5269, 2021
- [7] Salonikios V., Nitas M., Raptis S., and Yioultis T. V., "Computational analysis of graphene-based periodic structures via a three-dimensional field-flux eigenmode Finite Element formulation," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research*, **92**, 157-167, 2020
- [8] Nitas M., Kafesaki M., and Arslanagić, S., "Metasurface characterization based on eigenmode analysis and averaging of electromagnetic fields," *Journal of Applied Physics*, **134**, 12, 2023
- [9] R. Marqués, F. Martín, & M. Sorolla, "Metamaterials with negative parameters: theory, design, and microwave applications," John Wiley & Sons, Vol. 183, 2011
- [10] Graglia, R. D., Uslenghi, P. L., and Zich, R. E. "Dispersion relation for bianisotropic materials and its symmetry properties," *IEEE Transactions on antennas and propagation*, **39**, 83-90 (1991)
- [11] Mackay T. and Lakhtakia A., "Electromagnetic anisotropy and bianisotropy: a field guide," World Scientific, 2010
- [12] A. Serdiukov, et al., "Electromagnetics of bi-anisotropic materials - Theory and Applications," Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, 2001.